

ANTHROPOPHAGIC ITERATIONS: A FEMINIST PERSPECTIVE ON MODERN BRAZILIAN ARCHITECTURE

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ABSTRACT

Lina Bo Bardi has more recently, in preparation for her 100th birthday, sparked international debate surrounding her multifaceted career. Although still widely unknown outside of Latin America, this newly found fascination clearly reflects a pressing need for female models in architecture historiography. At the same time, it also divulges the dangers of fetishized narratives regarding female role models, which often tend to isolate them and overlook socio-political structures supporting their work. In that regard, this paper aims to map some of Lina's main influences and collaborations: a combination of European avant-gardes and Brazilian artistic movements; with an emphasis on her role in defining the latter. Marked by her experiential time in Bahia, Bo Bardi ultimately put forward an approach to popular culture that was grounded in defying realities and dismantling the status quo. In the core of her diversified and fluid practice lied an appetite for equality against cultural oppression and sociopolitical hierarchies. With that in mind, I argue that to disregard the role of gender from the analysis of her oeuvre and trajectory is to underestimate its power. Combining forces with the Tropicália movement, Bo Bardi sought *anthropophagic iterations* in order to understand the local culture, transform and equalize paternalistic structures of power regarding race, class, and gender. Ultimately, I hope that, by putting Lina Bo Bardi's work into a larger context of an interdisciplinary and political movement such as Tropicália, her scholarship can be perceived as truly political and dialectical, rather than exceptional.

Keywords: Lina Bo Bardi, Gender studies, Feminism, Anthropophagy, Tropicália.

ITERAÇÕES ANTROPOFÁGICAS: UMA PERSPECTIVA FEMINISTA DA ARQUITETURA MODERNA BRASILEIRA

RESUMO

Lina Bo Bardi, mais recentemente, em preparação para o seu 100º aniversário, tem provocado grande debate internacional em torno de sua carreira multifacetada. Apesar de ainda ser amplamente desconhecida fora da América Latina, esse recente fascínio pela sua figura reflete uma necessidade urgente de modelos femininos na historiografia de arquitetura. Ao mesmo tempo, informa sobre os perigos de narrativas fetichizadas de figuras históricas femininas, que por vezes as isolam e ignoraram as estruturas sociopolíticas que apoiam seu trabalho. A este respeito, este trabalho pretende traçar algumas das principais influências e colaborações de Lina: uma combinação de vanguardas europeias e movimentos artísticos brasileiros; com ênfase em seu papel na definição do último. Marcada por seu tempo experimental na Bahia, Bo Bardi, em última instância, preconizaria uma abordagem da cultura popular baseada em desafiar realidades e desarticular o status quo. O impulso por igualdade contra opressão cultural e hierarquias sociopolíticas representam o cerne de sua prática diversificada e fluida. Com isso em mente, argumento que desconsiderar o papel de gênero na análise de sua obra e trajetória é subestimar o poder de seu legado. Combinando forças com o movimento Tropicália, Bo Bardi buscou por *iterações antropofágicas* para melhor entender a cultura local, transformar, e equalizar estruturas paternalistas de poder em relação à raça, classe e gênero. Em última análise, espero que, ao colocar o trabalho de Lina Bo Bardi em um contexto mais compreensivo de um movimento interdisciplinar e político como o da Tropicália, sua historiografia possa ser percebida como verdadeiramente política e dialética, em vez de excepcional.

Keywords: Lina Bo Bardi, Estudos de gênero, Feminismo, Antropofagia, Tropicália.

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RESUMEN

Lina Bo Bardi, en preparación para su 100 aniversario, ha provocado un gran debate internacional en torno a su carrera polifacética. A

pesar de ser ampliamente desconocida fuera de América Latina, esta reciente fascinación por su figura refleja una necesidad urgente de modelos femeninos en la historiografía de arquitectura. Al mismo tiempo, informa sobre los peligros de narrativas fetichistas de figuras históricas femeninas, que a veces las aíslan e ignoran las estructuras socio-políticas que apoyan su trabajo. A este respecto, este trabajo pretende trazar algunas de las principales influencias y colaboraciones de Lina: una combinación de vanguardias europeas y movimientos artísticos brasileños; con énfasis en su papel en la definición del último. Marcada por su tiempo experimental en Bahía, Bo Bardi, en última instancia, preconizaría un enfoque de la cultura popular basada en desafiar realidades y desarticular el status quo. El impulso por igualdad contra la opresión cultural y las jerarquías socio-políticas representan el núcleo de su práctica diversa y fluida. Con eso en mente, argumento que desconsiderar el papel de género en el análisis de su obra y trayectoria es subestimar el poder de su legado. Combinando fuerzas con el movimiento Tropicália, Bo Bardi buscó "iteraciones antropofágicas" para entender mejor la cultura local, transformar, y ecualizar estructuras paternalistas de poder en relación a raza, clase y género. En última instancia, espero que al poner el trabajo de Lina Bo Bardi en un contexto más comprensivo de un movimiento interdisciplinario y político como el de la Tropicália, su historiografía pueda ser percibida como verdaderamente política y dialéctica, en vez de excepcional.

Palabras clave: Lina Bo Bardi, Estudios de género, Feminismo, Antropofagia, Tropicália.

Lina Bo Bardi scholarship has seen a recent revival internationally. Although profusely researched and studied in Brazil since the 1990s, she is still widely unknown outside of Latin America. More recently, in anticipation of her 100th birthday, Bo Bardi has sparked an international debate surrounding her multifaceted career, especially her anthropological take on architecture process and writing. In a context of male-dominated historiography, it is only fair that Lina Bo Bardi be the ultimate point of departure for investigating alternative practices in architectural history. As one of the twentieth-century's most influential architects, Lina Bo Bardi (1914-1992) applied her humanistic design philosophy fluidly to multiple endeavors: architecture, stage design, curatorship, editing, teaching, illustration, furniture, and fashion design. This way, the female Italian émigré and naturalized Brazilian would change the course of Brazilian art and architecture.

This newly found fascination clearly reflects a pressing need for alternative models in the field considering that twenty-five years after her death, women are still underrepresented in the specialized literature. At the same time, it also divulges into the dangers of fetishized perspectives of female role models, which often tend to isolate them and overlook the complexities and contradictions of their history. Olivia de Oliveira, one of Bo Bardi's main and first scholars, alerts us to the danger of fetishizing practicing women architects:

Lina's work has been mediated, manipulated, and fetishized by critics, historians, post-feminists, and global branch artists, with texts that respond to editorial and academic commercial demand, if not second-hand collages bordering on plagiarism. The celebrations, it is common fact, open wings to oblivion and alienation.

(OLIVEIRA, 2016, p. 161)

This alienation tends to see such exceptional personalities as isolated figures in history, brought up by chance and disassociated from a specific and supporting context. Contextualization of such figures is instrumental in legitimizing alternative non-western and potentially feminist approaches to architectural practice and education. A synchronic approach to Lina Bo Bardi's body of work, especially during her time in Bahia, talks to the collaboration and cross-contamination

that happened between disciplines and that contributed to her originality. In Bo Bardi's career, partnerships with male counterparts represented strategies to achieve higher and collective goals.

Equally lacking in the literature is a deeper understanding of the social and political engagement of Latin American avant-garde movements, which, unlike their European counterparts, have been largely dismissed. According to Claus Clüver, preference to the literary perspectives and the compartmentalization of academic discourse have led analysis to be restricted to *movements and individual contributions* isolating and laying aside performative, musical, visual, and architectonic aspects. This is especially true in the case of the *Semana de Arte Moderna* (Week of Modern Art) of 1922, a celebration of Brazil's centennial independence and an effort of emancipation from foreign models, which had a far stronger presence in the visual arts. (CLÜVER, 2006, pp. 161-162) This has skewed views of the manifestations in the arts and their relationships to each other. Almost a hundred years later, this historical avant-garde and its influence in defining neo-avant-gardes in the postwar are still under theorized.

Hence, combining both investigations, my goal is to map Lina Bo Bardi's influences and collaborations leading to the formation of reactionary and anthropophagic artistic movements in the context of the Brazilian dictatorship (1964-1985). By putting Lina Bo Bardi's work into a larger context of an interdisciplinary and political movement such as *Tropicália*, her scholarship can be perceived as truly political and dialectical, rather than exceptional. I argue that Lina Bo Bardi's trajectory was not only contended by ostracism by the local architecture scene, which led her to innovatively find ways of survival, but that she actively contributed to the *Tropicália* movement as a strategic way of proposing a new paradigm for the arts, which, for her, could not be disconnected from theory, criticism, and political praxis. Although this is not largely supported by existing architectural scholarship, there are plenty of evidences in Bo Bardi's collaborations in theater, cinema, art, and education, as well as ratifications in her vested and comprehensive interest in popular culture. By using the anthropophagic analogy of her work, I argue that Bo Bardi's avant-garde and revolutionary premises were direct responses to her socio-political context, which equally and actively encompasses her gender. Although her work was fed by the local and specific conditions found in the tropicalism culture of Brazil, she offered her own interpretation back to be seen as a tool towards outperforming colonizing effects and to give agency to the

"subaltern".¹ Similarly, this ethos can be seen in the gender delimitations she has found over the course of her career, to which she proposed alternative paths to the white-male predominant environment of architectural practice.

A FEMINIST APPROACH

As one of its main premises in architecture, feminism has aimed to fuse together theory and practice, individuals and systems, practitioner and process in order to identify "structural limitations and envision dissolving barriers". (STRATIGAKOS, 2012) The practice of art-historical monographs and mythology about artistic achievement of women tends to perpetuate the attitudes they initially tried to subsume by omitting their context and the dialectics of their paths. According to Linda Nochlin, systems rather than individuals have a further effect on the perceptions and opportunities available to each individual:

Thus the question of women's equality - in art as in any other realm - devolves not upon the relative benevolence or ill-will of individual men, nor the self-confidence or abjectness of individual women, but rather on the very nature of our institutional structures themselves and the view of reality which they impose on the human beings who are part of them. (LINDA NOCHLIN, 1989, p. 152)

On that note, Nochlin's "Why Have There Been No Great Women Artists?" is pivotal in questioning the role of academia and institutions in general as complicit on such omissions and skewed perspectives on the inferiority of women and on the *artistic genius* for men. False notions of "free-enterprise conception of individual achievement" and inherent artistic talent has unquestionably created for women an illusion of a "syllogism: if women had the golden nugget of artistic genius then it would reveal itself." (NOCHLIN, 1959, p. 152)

1. This is consistent with Antonio Gramsci's (1891-1937) philosophy of praxis. Gramsci was an Italian Marxist and Communist theorist and politician whose interpretation of Karl Marx's historical materialism has influenced not only Lina Bo Bardi but other members of the *Tropicália* movement, especially Glauber Rocha's *Aesthetics of Hunger* (1965), as it will be further explored throughout the paper.

This false perception could be well applied in the case of Bo Bardi's scholarship, often portrayed as a sole female heroine, under the same molds as their male counterparts' monographs, oblivious to questions of gender. These rely on a unique actor that exceptionally thrived despite the silent work division that has marked the architectural practice of the twentieth century. Alternatively, one could analyze this state of exception within the context of knowledge and practice that thread together with those realities and trajectories. According to Silvana Rubino, "the register of exceptionality only makes sense if situated within a broader exception than its singular qualities: within a set of circumstances that have been combined in a uncommon fashion." Moreover, to use gender, as a conditioning aspect of her work, is to think about it relationally, that is, "confronting two orders of hierarchy: gender and artistic genre." (RUBINO, 2010, p. 334-335)

According to Rubino, unquestioned dualities under those lenses neglect to reveal concealed preconceptions seen as universally accepted. In the Bauhaus pedagogy for example, the idea of an European and historic heritage, seen as oppressive, was portrayed as *female* and *maternal*. This same premise would be applied in conceptions of popular and mass culture, to be perceived as irrational and feminine, as opposed to the desired western industry and rational design premises endorsed by a *progressive* ideal. The roles of women in architecture, modernism, and avant-gardes were pre-defined explicitly, as in the case of Bauhaus where they directed to the weaving and ceramic, or subtly. (RUBINO, 2010, p. 336, 337 e 360)

Similarly, Nochlin proposes that questions and investigations in scholarship should focus on the conditions of producing art, having in mind that "genius" is rather a "dynamic activity rather than a static essence" molded actively by its environment: (NOCHLIN, 1989, p. 147-158)

the total situation of art making, both in terms of the development of the art maker and in the nature and quality of the work of art itself, occur in a social situation, are integral elements of this social structure, and are mediated and determined by specific and definable social institutions, be they art academies, systems of patronage, mythologies of the divine creator, artist as he-man or social outcast." (NOCHLIN, 1989, p. 155)

Lina Bo Bardi's work was primarily and undoubtedly an ongoing research in architecture, art, exhibition design, writing, in which cultural

experimentations and collaborations were an intrinsic part of her ethos. Itinerant between two countries, six cities, and innumerable partnerships, Bo Bardi adapted to each local condition as an active agent in search of collective knowledge and initiating social and artistic engagements, which, one could argue, created an alternative type of modernism.

Gender was not necessarily a flag for Bo Bardi's actions as she would be content to be one of the boys (even by calling herself an *architetto*, gender neutral word in Italian for architect, as opposed to *arquiteta*, feminine correspondent in Portuguese). (FERRAZ, 1993, p. 327) However, the interdisciplinarity, the collectivity, the sensitivity to local issues, the everyday life, and the humanity aspects that have inspired her work are undeniably the opposite principles of just *one of the guys*.

On the one hand, Lina provoked and challenged the status quo by using premises from the national-popular culture, through a Marxist perspective. The Valéria Cirell house (1958), in São Paulo, expresses that as one of the less famous exemplars of her alternative architecture and closely related to Antonio Gramsci's "philosophy of praxis" (CARRANZA, 2014, p. 136). For Gramsci, in analyzing the philosophical premises of the historic materialism of Karl Marx, the "intellectual" has a fundamental societal role in the popular emancipation, whose knowledge is however of no greater meaning than the popular. On the intellectuals, who should be embedded in society organically as well as fully engaged with its socio-political dynamics, rely the responsibility of producing cultural actions that are transforming and liberating. This role has the potential of establishing philosophical and existentialist questions while acting in the *field*, which should aim for a popular-empowering-new culture. (GRINOVER, 2009, p. 11)

Regarding the infamous 1989's quote: "I never faced any obstacles, not even as a woman. That's why I say I am Stalinist and anti-feminist," attributed to Bo Bardi, Zeuler R. M. de A. Lima puts it into perspective, contending that Bo Bardi saw in Stalin a true hero the liberation of Italy from fascism and that her issues with the current feminist women's liberation movement of that time was that it was white and bourgeoisie dominated. Therefore, the misinterpretation of her words might lead to the false impression of an apolitical position regarding her gender. (LIMA, 2013) As Esther da Costa Meyer points out, like many other female peers, Lina fought firstly for humanity causes rather than feminism, embracing commissions that lacked personal signatures, but rather adapted to local needs and conveyed strong political engagement. (MEYER, 2002) This deep commitment to a broader sense of equality, certainly contends gender, along with issues of class and race.

AN EUROPEAN (FEMININE) PATH TO THE TROPICS

Lina Bo Bardi, née Anchillina di Enrico Bo (1914-1992), graduated from the Scuola di Architettura in Rome under Gustavo Giovannoni and Marcello Piacentini at the age of 25 years old. Looking to get away from the traditionalism and limitations of Rome, Bo Bardi moved to Milan. In face of the war in Milan, in Lina's own words "when nothing was built, only destroyed," the alternative was to work as an illustrator and graphic designer. Many Italian publishers expanded their editorial lines toward interior decoration and women's magazines, as architects started to venture into the editorial world. Lina was one of them. Introduced to Giò Ponti by her former partner Carlos Pagani in 1940, in 1941 the three collaborated in the launching of the *Lo Stile* magazine. Although *Lo Stile* resembled Ponti's *Domus*, it had a more popular appeal and *less professional and educated flair*. Another collaborator of the new magazine was Pietro Maria Bardi, who was struggling to find writing commissions in Rome and would later become Lina's partner in a new life and projects in Brazil. (LIMA, 2013, p. 5-20)

Bo Bardi's take on the domestic world, furniture, and popular culture might reveal implications of the gender division of labor in the profession in that period. Although the place of women in architectural avant-gardes was often confined to domesticity or what was considered *lesser arts*, Lina Bo Bardi takes on a rather leadership role in promoting a forward thinking *feminine world*. Her residence in Brazil, the Glass House, in São Paulo, worked as a manifesto of a new type of architecture, an established male practice. However, it also highlighted a new gender perspective into the home. The kitchen of the house materialized a new style of home living and working, which leant onto more scientific and modern standards. These directly followed the trends initiated in the USA by Mary Peterson and Lillian Gilbreth (1915), which culminated in the *Frankfurt Kitchen* by Grette Schütte-Lihotsky in 1925. (RUBINO, 2010, p. 352-353) Bo Bardi's take on furniture design, especially in face of the lethargy of the industry in Brazil, shows her ability to find methods that were outside pre-established norms and to defy means of production and labor.

At the same time, Lina Bo Bardi and Pietro Maria Bardi's relationship is yet to be further explored as it represented an interesting combination to say the least. Politically, Lina was part of the Resistance and the clandestine Communist Party. However, in later meeting Pietro Mari Bardi, an art-dealer, journalist, who was also well

connected to the fascist regime, Bo Bardi proved her talent for political accommodation. Maybe not coincidentally, Bardi's aesthetic preferences along with his significant connections to some of the International Style's finest exponents in art and architecture were of great significance in Lina's path, especially in establishing her commissions in Brazil. (MEYER, 2002)

Arriving in São Paulo in 1946, under Assis Chateaubriand's sponsorship, Lina Bo and Pietro Maria Bardi worked copiously to envision and place the new Museu de Arte de São Paulo - Masp (Museum of Art of São Paulo) as the core of a cultural action plan towards industrialization - in reference to the European model that happened between WWI and WWII. The efforts involved the creation of a School of industrial design, propaganda and the arts (Instituto de Arte Contemporânea), a sophisticated art, culture, and architecture magazine (Habitat), and an industrial design enterprise (Estúdio de Arte Palma). Lina used the pages of *Habitat* to disseminate the initiatives in Brazil towards a "greater social commitment in modern architecture," highlighting projects by Vilanova Artigas. (ANELLI, 2012) Bo Bardi used museography, curatorship, and education as explicit tools to disseminate the production of these forward-thinking cultural premises to the masses. Bo Bardi's specific concern with industrial design reveals a clear reference back to the Bauhaus and New Objectivity movements in Germany, in which she establishes a strong relationship between the idea of Brazilian "pré-artesanato doméstico esparso" ("sparse and domestic pre-craftsmanship") and modernity. This idea related to a refusal of the idea of a universal linear history and the recognition of a local and unique capitalist development since Colonial Brazil, which, unlike Europe, happened without a feudal historic occurrence. (RIBEIRO, 2014, p. 8)

In 1957, as part of the application process for the position of Chair in the Theory of Architecture at Architecture and Urbanism Faculty at the University of São Paulo - FAU USP, Bo Bardi produced a thesis entitled *Propaedeutic Contribution to the Teaching of the Theory of Architecture* that would represent the epitome of her philosophical approach to architecture, in which education was central to defy and reject the ideal of the *individualistic architect*. The non-chronological narrative of her thesis connected ancient thinkers and theoreticians along with her contemporaries, embedding ideas of memory and past in practice, wedding theory and practice as one. Because these ideas represented a major paradigm shift, Bo Bardi was faced with great resistance by the established faculty of the school. Bo Bardi has reported that she was not

only initially denied the opportunity to apply, but that the position was dissolved after her insistence. (OLIVEIRA, 2006, p. 249-250)

In 1958, after two years as a lecturer and being denied a tenured position in the FAU USP, Bo Bardi is invited to be a visiting scholar in the University of Bahia's School of Fine Arts, in Salvador, where she structured the Architecture and Urbanism course with Diógenes Rebouças. There she would first get exposed to Brazil's popular culture and find the grounds for her cultural and professional efflorescence, as part of University of Bahia's dean Edgar Santos and state governor Juracy Magalhães who aimed for a total renovation and modernization of Bahia's culture.

Bahia is the state in which Brazil's first capital was located and, therefore, the one with the strongest African cultural influence. In collaboration with the theatre director, Eros Martim Gonçalves, from Bahia University's Theatre Faculty, Bo Bardi produced a critical and innovative exhibition called *Bahia no Ibirapuera* at the Fifth São Paulo Biennial in 1959, elucidating the direction her research is moving towards at that point. Syncretism, everyday life, humble materials, and the performative aspect of the local culture seem especially intriguing to her artistic investigation.

Ultimately, Bo Bardi would become the director of the Museu de Arte Moderna da Bahia (Museum of Modern Art of Bahia) and the Museu de Arte Popular (Museum of Popular Art), between 1959 and 1964. (OLIVEIRA, 2014, p. 153) This period would be critical in refining Lina's commitment to Brazil's native and popular culture aligned with her research in design and exhibition practices. Despite its less prominent economic representation and hardships, Northeastern Brazil is singularly rich in art and culture, and, as its oldest region, constitutes the basis of the country and its people. According to Olivia de Oliveira, Lina's influences go back to:

two main avant-garde resistance movements against, and for liberation from, the cultural domination under which Latin America was suffering: first, the Movimento modernista Antropófago of Oswald de Andrade, Tarsila do Amaral and Mário de Andrade, which arose in 1922 and left its mark in Brazilian art, literature, and architecture up until the nineteen-forties/fifties; secondly, the Tropicália movement founded by Glauber Rocha, Caetano Veloso, and Zé Celso in the late nineteen-sixties, which harmonizes perfectly with the modernist approach. (OLIVEIRA, 2014, p. 153)

Bahia would prove to be a fertile ground for many other partnerships, between Bo Bardi and other locals and foreigner intellectual and artists, who like her felt an incredible potential in the richness of its popular culture. All of Bo Bardi's collaboration from this period would fundamentally impact future artistic and socio-political movements.

ESTABLISHING AN AVANT-GARDE IN BAHIA

How to explain, in an underdeveloped country, the appearance of an avant-garde and justify it not as symptomatic alienation, but as a decisive factor in collective progress? (OITICICA, 1967, p. 11)

During the 1960s, Bahia was going through an unprecedented cultural effervescence, also referred to as *período das luzes* or *renascimento baiano* (lights period or Bahian renaissance). This effort, mostly led by the University of Bahia's dean, Edgard Santos, reflects the developmentalist *zeitgeist* of the time, between Juscelino Kubitschek's and João Goulart's presidencies, which resulted in Brasília, *Bossa Nova*, and the Concrete Poetry. Worldwide, we are talking about the Cold War, the Cuban Revolution, and other anti-colonialist movements.

According to Antonio Risério the origins of the *Tropicália* come from a syncretic nature only possible through the efforts of Edgar Santos, the dean of the University of Bahia, in combining European *émigrés* with instrumental figures of the local popular culture. (RISÉRIO, 1995, p. 135-155) Although hybridization was the norm, the idea of anthropophagy carried through the century supporting efforts towards a national cultural independence. As one of the strongest figures connected to the local institutions of education and cultural dissemination (Universidade Federal da Bahia and Museu de Arte Moderna da Bahia), Lina Bo Bardi pushed disciplinary boundaries of artistic and architectural production, making connections, and inspiring others.

Edgar Santos engaged in a varied array of cultural fields, aiming to establish an intellectual and cultural syncretism between "a white Bahia, poor in spirit and a black Bahia, poor in opportunities." (GRINOVER, 2009, p. 3) Santos proposed an academic exchange that fostered meetings between local and foreign artists in performance and theater (Eros Martim Gonçalves from Recife), music (Hans Joaquim Koellreutter from Germany, disciple of Arnold Schönberg), dance (Yanka Rudzka from Poland), philosophy (Agostinho da Silva from Portugal),

among others. They all had in common a “rebellious political attitude towards the phony social and cultural values of a decaying bourgeoisie.” (OLIVEIRA, 2014, p. 156) Among the main promoters of the avant-garde action were Koellreutter’s Music Seminar, Bo Bardi’s Museum of Modern Art, and da Silva’s Centro de Estudos Afro-Orientais (Center of Eastern-African Studies), having Eros Martim Gonçalves and the Theater School working as the mediators of the University-Museum axis. This prolific and collaborative environment would eventually lead to the next revolutionary generation, among who were Glauber Rocha and Caetano Veloso, proponents of Cinema Novo and Tropicalist music, respectively. Although these were directly influenced by the aesthetics and practices of the time (*nouvelle vague*, *Bossa Nova*, to name a few), Bo Bardi’s and Koellreutter’s legacies rely on the formative aspect of their sensitivity towards a “pedagogy of restlessness and freedom.” (RISÉRIO, 1995, p. 23-26)

These were the circumstances in which Lina developed her “ideological plantation” project, which connected the popular culture from Indian and African roots to the collective pedagogical revolution inspired by Paulo Freire’s work, named *Movimentos de educação de base* (foundational education movements), placing “more value on its [Brazil’s] traditional forms of knowledge.” (OLIVEIRA, 2014, pp. 156-157) At the same time that Bo Bardi elaborated the proposal for the Museu de Arte Moderna da Bahia, she was also concerned with the creation of the Museu de Arte Popular and the School of Industrial Design connected to it. The latter had the aim of empowering local communities through the production of industrial design items brought up from an acquired and traditional knowledge. (GRINOVER, 2014, p. 5) In her perspective the Museum of Modern and Popular Culture:

Our institution is not a Museum, the term is not appropriate: a museum conserves, and we don’t have a collection yet. Ours must be called a Center, a Movement, a School and its future collection, one well-programmed in accordance with lasting didactic and not occasional criteria, should be called: a Permanent Exhibition. That’s the sense we mean when we use the term Museum.

(BARDI. In FERRAZ, 2008, p. 139)

This quote sheds light on the ultimate kernel of Bo Bardi’s efforts: education and research. Bo Bardi saw on education and local and inherited

practices the effective means to develop new value chains towards an empowered and independent local society. In a type of backward anthropophagy practice, as a foreigner, she fully embraced the local culture, encouraging its development and independence from European and western influences. The anthropophagic act in Bo Bardi's work in Bahia is, therefore, twofold: it goes back and forth, once Bo Bardi re-utilizes this newly found paradigm to ritualistically dismantle local hierarchical barriers of class, race, and potentially, gender. In its peak, within the Tropicalist movement, these efforts would carry on Oswald de Andrade's anthropophagus premise with a twist: hybridized by the European presences in Bahia during its renaissance period of the 1960s.

This is consistent with one of the main premises influencing many of the twentieth-century's artistic movements: anthropophagy, proposed by Oswald de Andrade's *Manifesto Antropofágico (Anthropophagous Manifesto)* of 1928, during the *Semana de Arte Moderna de 1922 (Modern Art Week of 1922)*. The concept of anthropophagy is inspired by a Tupi-Guarani war rite, and represents "a metaphor for the repudiation, assimilation, and triumph." (NUNES, 2004, p. 57) According to Benedito Nunes, it is precisely:

a catalytic term that mobilizes numerous negations into one, a pitiless symbol for the practice of cannibalism. A blend of insult sacrilege, it is a surrogate for verbal attack on an immaterial, protean, and multisided enemy. Among this enemy's many aspects are remnants of the repressive, politico-religious, and burdensome colonial baggage on which Brazilian civilization was founded. Its legacy was a patriarchal society with established models for behavior and messianic expectations, with intellectual rhetoric that mimicked the metropolis and succumbed to foreign ways, as well as nativism that sublimated the failure of being colonized by imitating the customs of the colonizer. (NUNES, 2004, p. 57)

for the antropófagos] the solution to the antagonism of social interests lay at the frontier of economics and politics. In short, the antropófagos, en route to Utopia, considered politics the redistribution of social goods, as it returned power, divested of any authoritarian aura, to society. Consequently, society, that great matriarch, uninhibited

through catharsis [anthropophagy] of its instincts and liberated from the censorship of the paternalistic superego [dictatorship], would, in realizing its highest potential, become a free communion of men. (NUNES, 2004, p. 61)

According to Sergio Miceli, the Anthropophagus movement accrues from a characteristic ambivalence between backwardness and progress, cosmopolitan ambitions and peripheral condition, characteristic of Latin American contexts. At the same time that the language was a constraint in its dissemination, leading it to be mostly local, "it dilated the margins of creative explosion due to the readjustments and recycling it had to submit the borrowings made from the European models." (MICELI, 2012, p. 21) This *dilatation* was the main propeller of other future movements. According to both Vera Bastazin, (Bastazin, 1992, p. 8) and Sônia Salztein (SALZTEIN, 2006, p. 13) it was not until the 1950s and 1960s that Brazilian modernism would reach its peak, following the rupture proposed by the Modern Art Week of 1922, taking ultimately the forms of Tropicalism, *Cinema Novo*, and concrete poetry.

Tropicália represented a synthesis of dialogue between the different avant-garde discourses between the 1950s and 1960s, beyond anthropophagy: the *Cinema Novo*, *Bossa Nova*, *Concretismo* and *Neoconcretismo*, and the *Teatro Arena*, aiming to establish a cultural phenomenon grounded in political, social, and ethical terms. According to Ferreira Gullar, "political, anthropological, and folkloric data" were mixed in order to question "the discourses and the images of Brazilian culture created between dichotomies: open and alienated art, as well as national and foreign, popular and mass art" and unchain a "radical transformation." Pushing forward de Andrade's aesthetic premises towards a political and economic dimension, this new culture of experimentation and hybridization could colonize back the western references. (JEZZINI, 2010, pp. 60-67) Differently from the Anthropophagus movement, which exalted the povo (masses), *Tropicália* celebrated the everyday life of urban citizens, encompassing issues of "race, gender, sexuality, and personal freedom," however still under the premise of "critically devouring influxes from abroad." (BASUALDO, 2005, p. 3) This agenda, not coincidentally, aligned well with Lina's premises in education, museography, and architecture production.

According to Oiticica's *General Scheme of the New Objectivity*: "The avant-garde phenomenon in Brazil is no longer an issue for an isolated elite group, but, rather, a broad cultural issue with great repercussions in

need of collective solutions." (DUNN, 2001, p. 13) In the case of the *Tropicália* movement, it was an immediate response to the 1964's coup-d'état, which marked the beginning of the 20-year period of military dictatorship in Brazil. The movement as a whole was a critique of the repression as well as a celebration of Brazilian culture, exacerbated by stereotypical representations and allegories of the country as a tropical paradise (which originated the name), "only to subvert them with pointed references to political violence and social misery." (BASUALDO, 2005, p. 3) Among its main exponents are Glauber Rocha, Hélio Oiticica, José Celso Martinez, and Caetano Veloso. Together they who saw the emphasis on popular culture from "orthodox left-wing thinker" as superficial and an inhibitor of "the possibility of elaborating an effective and mobilizing critical stance on contemporary Brazilian culture and its place in the international context." (BASUALDO, 2005, p. 12)

As opposed to conceiving popular culture as the *result of a process*, tropicalistas aimed the process as the goal in itself, establishing great dynamism between the arts. The focus of the movement relied on the performative and the collective aspects of Northeastern popular expressions, such as carnival, music, and street art, which culminated in Oiticica's exploration of the *favelas* in his famous *Tropicália* installation, presented in 1967 at the MoMA (Museum of Modern Art). This performative aspect of art, centered on the spectator, who was no longer just a viewer but an engaging actor in the scene, would use popular culture as the tool "revolutionize the contents and forms of enunciation [...] to do so in a way that would be attractive to a wide audience, an audience whose members were increasingly summoned as participants in the context of these practices." (BASUALDO, 2005, p. 14) This would follow an ongoing research by Bo Bardi's museography and exhibition design practices, influenced by 1930s European and Soviet avant-garde movements, in which its political aspect was the key in moving the gaze away from the gallery walls, e.g. Masp's *Exposição didática da História da Arte* (1947), *Bahia no Ibirapuera* (1959), *Nordeste* (1963), Masp's Inaugural exhibition (1968), and *A Mão do Povo Brasileiro* (1969).

Lina Bo Bardi, who had been collaborating thoroughly in theater after the coup d'état, found in her curatorial and pedagogical approach to architecture the means of expression and resistance in the midst of a dry-spell of new commissions. According to Glauber Rocha, Lina Bo Bardi was his mentor and collaborator, as he places her work in leading the Museu de Arte Moderna da Bahia and the stage production for Brecht's *The Threepenny Opera* with Eros Martim Gonçalves as one

the main milestones of the movement and a “call to war with the province.” (OLIVEIRA, 2016) In Glauber Rocha's terms, under a similar tone to Oswald de Andrade's pau-brasil and anthropophagy manifestos:

The war that the new generations must open against the province must be immediate: the cultural action of the University and the Museum of Modern Art are two shock tanks [...] the horns of the battle were played by the great exhibitions of the Museum of Modern Art and by the montage of Brecht's *Ópera dos Três Tostões* (The threepenny opera), which created great excitement in the little-bourgeois thought. The stimulation of the press, which must lose the most foolish preconceptions of language, would be the third time to win [...] Against the 'doctorism,' the oratory, the public square mythology, against the tie and the mustache. [...] it is being defeated in the province the own province: defeated in its own conventional language, in its own taboo against the freedom of loving, in its own convenience of garment, in its own laws against revolution [...] I would like that everyone of you that leads our true thought would engage in taking Bahia one step farther. (RISÉRIO, 1995, p. 14-15)

Towards *An Aesthetics of Hunger (Uma Estética da Fome)*, Glauber Rocha's Cinema Novo “sought to construct an anti-aspirational mode of movie-making, contingent on local circumstances; it stood in critical relation to Hollywood.” Rocha took *advantage* of the international perception of Brazilian culture as primitive, due to its post-colonial conditions as well as a general taste for its fetishization, shedding light onto social issues of poverty and the numbness of the general audience. Cinema Novo was a revolutionary attempt to give agency and consciousness to minorities through a 'raw,' 'miserable,' and 'violent' aesthetics.

This is the fundamental situation of the arts in Brazil today: many distortions, especially the formal exoticism that vulgarizes social problems, have provoked a series of misunderstandings that involve not only art but also politics. For the European observer the process of artistic creation in the underdeveloped world is of interest only insofar as it satisfies a nostalgia for primitivism. This primitivism is generally

presented as a hybrid form, disguised under the belated heritage of the *civilized world*, a heritage poorly understood since it is imposed by colonial conditioning. Latin America remains, undeniably, a colony, and what distinguishes yesterday's colonialism from today's colonialism is merely the more polished form of the colonizer and the more subtle forms of those who are preparing future domination. The international problem of Latin America is still a case of merely exchanging colonizers. Our possible liberation will probably come, therefore, in the form of a new dependency. This economic and political conditioning has led us to philosophical weakness and impotence that engenders sterility when conscious and hysteria when unconscious. It is for this reason that the hunger of Latin America is not simply an alarming symptom: it is the essence of our society. There resides the tragic originality of Cinema Novo in relation to world cinema. Our originality is our hunger and our greatest misery is that this hunger is felt but not intellectually understood. We understand the hunger that the European and the majority of Brazilians have not understood. For the European it is a strange tropical surrealism. For the Brazilian it is a national shame. He does not eat, but he is ashamed to say so; and yet, he does not know where this hunger comes from. We know—since we made these sad, ugly films, these screaming, desperate films where reason does not always prevail—that this hunger will not be cured by moderate governmental reforms and that the cloak of Technicolor cannot hide, but only aggravates, its tumors. Therefore, only a culture of hunger, weakening its own structures, can surpass itself qualitatively; the most noble cultural manifestation of hunger is violence. (ROCHA, 1965, p. 13)

The consciousness-raising politics and embracing of poverty as a cultural empowerment device would later on be appropriated by the Brazilian left and gained strength through Paulo Freire's *Pedagogy of the Oppressed* (1976), Augusto Boal's *Theater of the Oppressed*, and Lina Bo Bardi's own concept of *Arquitetura Pobre* (Poor Architecture). This *movement of the oppressed* would embrace the qualities of poverty, unlike other contemporaneous approaches reliant on its denial, proposing instead a much humbler alternative. However, far

from being unambitious, it sought to acknowledge Brazil's condition of underdevelopment as an opportunity to draw by example an alternate type of society. (WILLIAMS, 2006, p. 200-204)

In the context of the Brazilian dictatorship (1964-1985), which forced Lina to move back to São Paulo from Salvador, she wrote: "during the difficult moments of a country's history, when structures fall apart, mysticism is the last way to save humankind from passivity" (OLIVEIRA, 2014, p. 164). According to De Oliveira, Lina's "approach to the city of Salvador played a key role in this movement toward the mythopoeic as related to Afro-Bahian popular culture." (OLIVEIRA, 2014, p. 159) This subversion of foreign determinisms and the combination of an ethical and political agenda puts Bo Bardi in comparison to other similar movements happening in Latin America, led by Diego Rivera and Juan O'Gorman. (OLIVEIRA, 2014, p. 162) In this context of Latin American artistic insurgencies, it is particularly relevant, her role as a woman leading one of the many fronts of the broader Brazilian movement. Even though gender was not an explicit flag, her consistent political agenda against the pre-established and patriarchal structures of society shows significant engagement with similar causes to feminism. Like Bo Bardi, branching out of poststructuralist and postcolonial theories, a feminist approach to architecture would be also committed to dismantling power relationships of dominant-dominated, oppressing-oppressed, male-female, and center-periphery.

CONCLUSIONS

By placing Lina in the context of other intellectuals, cultural agitators, and artists, my goal is to demystify the emphasis given to the study of the production originated from her European background, which weakens the prolific dialectical discourse then and now still surrounding her work in Brazil. The romantic idea of Lina Bo Bardi as a lonely *heroine*, although it emphasizes her talent and unique trajectory, it also isolates and limits the dialectical potential of encouraging the inclusion of feminist perspectives to the existing scholarship. Exacerbated by her gender, this alienation and the myth of Lina Bo Bardi as the only one working with the people needs to be demystified, problematized, and historicized in the context of supporting Brazilian avant-gardes, as opposed to those solely in Europe. This is often done in architectural historiography, in which Lina Bo Bardi is put in comparison to Charlotte Perriand and Lilly Reich, for the lack of other iconic models in similar contexts of Latin America or post-coloniality.

Drawing out of Lina Bo Bardi's legacy and philosophy, one must think relationally and contextually on the production of this period. An advocate for a humanistic and fluid approach to practice, Bo Bardi's oeuvre shows a keen interest in addressing the consequences of colonialism, slavery, and geopolitical power, having at its kernel values of equality, justice, and disruption of social and aesthetic hierarchies and boundaries. Thankfully Lina Bo Bardi was not alone and ultimately led a generation of agitators that, likewise, saw in the status quo a form of oppression and subordination, not only from a personal but collective and structural perspective. For those, inspired by Gramsci's "philosophy of praxis," only combined efforts in thinking and acting, through the mediation of the intellectual and its technical and dialectical potential, could propose a new model of culture based on a critical and popular self-government, in lieu of a patriarchal and backwards archetype still trapped in colonial and rural values. In that sense, to neglect gender-based conditional circumstances of her trajectory is to contradict her own principles. Furthermore, Lina Bo Bardi's work in Brazil offers an obvious point of departure in establishing a consistent line of research on gender and women in architecture, as well as on feminism and political engagement practices, both needed and still highly under theorized in the specialized literature.

Similarly, the *Tropicália* movement and its implications on the modernist and postmodernist era of Brazilian culture and artistic production must not be underestimated. As the epitome of a socio-political engaged effort, more research needs to address the process of artistic production of the 1950s, 1960s, and 1970s, focusing on the synergy and cross-contamination between all the arts and their expressions, as a unified response to an unreliable political establishment, stemming from a still young nation and democracy.

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